

REAL TIME MONITORING OF COMPOSITE LAMINATED STRUCTURES WITH EMBEDDABLE SENSING LAYERS

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ABSTRACT

Fiber reinforced composite materials are currently essential for several engineering applications that need to combine high mechanical properties with very low structural weight. However, due to their heterogeneous composition, the failure mechanisms in composites are still very unpredictable, unlike that happens with steel or aluminum [1]. This leads to the need of applying real-time monitoring techniques in composites, through the incorporations of appropriated sensors into them, in order to ensure their safely work in service. This work presents a new layer concept to be embedded within carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) composite laminated structures, capable of real-time monitoring of their strain status. It contains strain gauges (SG) that can measure the evolution of strains in the internal laminae of structural composites and an electric circuit directly printed on its surface to transmit the data obtained to an acquisition system for further processing and analysis. Bulk CFRP/epoxy samples and equivalent ones containing embedded sensing film and regular polyimide films are submitted to interlaminar shear strength and tensile testing. With the former, it was possible to assess eventual effects on the adhesion between the layers of the composite, while the latter were used to evaluate the influence of the embedded film on the mechanical properties. Moreover, by placing an equivalent surface mounted SG, it was possible to directly compare strain data from the surface and the interior of the composite, thereby serving as validation method for the sensing circuit. The experiments carried out demonstrated that the proposed embedded sensing film allowed indeed accurately monitoring the internal strains developed within composites. Additionally, it was observed that the inserted embedded monitoring layers did not affect significantly the adhesion and mechanical properties of the CFRP composites, unlike what happened with the embedded polyimide layers.

1 INTRODUCTION

The application of composite materials has seen a significant increase in recent decades in several engineering fields, continuously replacing traditional metals such as steel or aluminum. Due to their high strength-to-weight ratio, achieved by combining high mechanical properties fibers with matrices capable of ensuring an efficient stress distribution, the production of parts and structures with high mechanical properties at low structural weights is achieved by multiple manufacturing techniques. In comparison to metals, this means that the mechanical performance is either equal or improved at more reduced fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions as well [2].

One of the issues of composites is the difficulty in predicting their mechanical performance and failure mechanisms at the loading conditions they need withstand by design, because of their inherent heterogenic and anisotropic nature. In addition, polymer matrix composites are sometimes brittle, which makes even more difficult predicting their in-service failure due to the high number of mechanisms involved in this process. It is of particular concern in aeronautic and aerospace applications that composites are also prone to barely visible impact damage (BVID), in which certain low-velocity

impacts caused by relatively small masses, can lead to delamination, fissures or even cracks in the composite laminate [1].

An increasing number of research has been carried out concerning these issues using structural health monitoring (SHM) solutions. Among them, the most auspicious monitoring concepts use built-in structural diagnostic systems containing a sensing network, integrated hardware and software to read and analyze the collected data in real-time during the service life of the composite structure. This is the main idea behind the use of “Embeddable monitoring layers” (EML), which are essentially thin flexible layers with sensing networks for being embedded, as additional layer between structural composite laminae, which are capable of monitoring and transmitting in real-time data regarding the current state of the host structure. When working with composites it is advisable to have such sensors embedded within their inner structure, as it is closer to internal damage sources, which are easier to detect due to the enhanced sensitivity caused from the stronger coupling with the structure [1, 3, 4]. Other advantages include the shielding from environmental factors [5], monitoring throughout the entire lifespan of the structure [6], noise reduction [7], less complexity due to the removal of wiring [8] and surface profile integrity preservation, which is extremely important in aeronautic applications, as aerodynamic efficiency is one of the critical design constrains [9].

It is also worth noting that embedding monitoring devices or sensing films increase the overall complexity of the manufacturing process of composites, mostly regarding difficulties in adhesion and incompatibility between the materials that are being embedded and the surrounding structural layers of the composite. When not properly addressed, the final part or structure could be more susceptible to the occurrence of geometrical defects, namely delamination or increased number of voids in the composite, which affect negatively the overall mechanical performance of the composite structure [10, 11].

This paper presents the development and validation of a new concept for EML to be inserted within CRFP laminated structures, for strain monitoring purposes. The novelty lies in the substrate of the film itself, which is a cured thin strip of epoxy resin, equal to that of the matrix of the composite, to prevent issues with delamination [12] in the interface between the EML and the adjacent structural layers. The experimental work was focused on the development of the EML by using vacuum bag infusion (VBI). Tensile tests are then carried out on bulk CFRP samples and the equivalent ones containing embedded EMLs and regular polyimide (PI) films, in order to verify the performance of the sensing circuit and to evaluate the influence of the inserted sensing films on the mechanical performance of composites. Another group of samples was submitted to ILSS tests to assess the overall adhesion properties. Comparisons are traced out between EML and PI films, as the latter is a very popular substrate used in the design of flexible sensing circuits, and has been embedded in composite materials for monitoring purposes [6, 13, 14].

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials and methods used for manufacturing the embeddable monitoring layers (EML)

The development of a new EML for internal strain monitoring to apply in polymer reinforced composite materials is presented. Its substrate is meant to be equal to that of the matrix of the composite laminate in which it is going to be inserted into, to achieve compatibility between the matrix of the composite and the EML itself. In this experimental work, the following epoxy resin is used for both of the aforementioned ends:

- Sicomin SR Infugreen 810 resin mixed, at mass fraction of 29%, with the SD4771 hardener.

The EML substrate is obtained by VBI, under the following procedure:

- After mixing the resin with the hardener, it should be impregnated, under vacuum, to the interior of a sealed bag that contains the mold of the film, as shown in Figure 1;
- The mold is composed of two glass plates, with Teflon layers to facilitate demolding, that are vacuum sealed inside a bag, with no observable air leaks. The resin flows between the two glasses, due to the prior application of layers of thin tape on one of the glasses. This ensures that

there is a cavity between the glasses from which the resin can slowly flow and form the film with the desired thickness. For this set of experiments, two layers of 50 μm non-absorbent tape were placed on the edges of a single glass in order to later obtain thin epoxy resin films with 100 μm of thickness;

- The resin fully cures after two days at room temperature. However, at this point, the epoxy resin is very brittle, and there is a serious risk of shattering the film when separating glass. Thus, the separation process needs to take place before the resin is completely cured. Multiple tests with the resin demonstrated that the glasses should be separated approximately 30 hours after resin impregnation. These values are of course completely dependent on the type of resin or matrix that is being utilized to fabricate the films;
- Upon separation, the thin epoxy film is stucked on the glass that contains the reference tape.

Figure 1 - VBI arrangement to manufacture the thin epoxy resin

The sensing circuit used in this work was designed for strain monitoring. It consists on a single bi-directional SG (Omega, model SGT-4/350-XY41 – with 350 Ω base resistance, 2.09 gauge factor and 30000 μm maximum strain), 4 manually screen printed silver ink (Dyoctec, model DM-SIP-2004) conductive tracks used to transmit strain data and 4 soldering terminals (HBM, model 1-LS4-G), from which it is possible to relay the strain data to an acquisition system capable for post-processing and analysis. The circuits can be directly mounted in the epoxy substrate, and since the Ag ink needs to undergo curing at temperatures between 80 and 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, the latter must still be attached to the glass, otherwise, the thin epoxy structure deforms irreversibly. Finally, the film can be detached from the glass plate, thus finalizing the manufacturing of the EML, as shown in Figure 2 a). The main characteristics of the film are its transparency, its low thickness, which was set at 100 μm , and its high flexibility, as can be seen in Figure 2 b).

Figure 2 - Epoxy substrate EML: a) view with SG sensing circuit; b) EML flexibility

2.2 Manufacture of CFRP samples

The EML was embedded in composite laminates and the manufactured samples were submitted to tensile and ILSS tests. In both experiments three groups of CFRP samples were compared: G1 containing

bulk CFRP samples with no embedded films, G2 including CFPR with embedded EML and G3 having CFRP samples with embedded a PI sensing films.

For both tests, the following sequences for each group of samples were adopted:

- G1 Tensile test (G1-T) sample configuration – $[0]_{3s}$
- G2 Tensile test (G2-T) sample configuration – $[0/0/0/EML/ISO/0/0/0/0]$
- G3 Tensile test (G3-T) sample configuration – $[0/0/0/PI/ISO/0/0/0/0]$
- G1-ILSS sample configuration – $[0]_{4s}$
- G2-ILSS sample configuration – $[0/0/0/0/EML/ISO/0/0/0/0]$
- G3-ILSS sample configuration – $[0/0/0/0/PI/ISO/0/0/0/0]$

The CFRP laminates were manufactured through VBI, in which each individual layer is stacked on a mold that is subsequently vacuum sealed, and then impregnated with epoxy resin and left to cure for approximately two days at room temperature. The structural layers were obtained from unidirectional carbon fiber fabric 350 UT from Rebelco, with areal weight of 350 g/m^2 , and for the specimens that contain PI sensing films, Kapton variant model 300 MT from DuPont, with 0.075 mm of thickness is used. To safeguard the electric circuit from adjacent conductive carbon layers, an additional thin strip of epoxy resin (reference ISO), obtained from the same procedure that is described in section 2.1, is placed on top of the circuit.

The tensile test samples were prepared accordingly ASTM D3039/D3039M standard, while the ones for ILSS ones followed the procedure of ISO 14130:1997 standard. However, to ensure that the internal strain data is being collected from the samples with EML and PI sensing films that are submitted to tensile testing, it was necessary to slightly increase their width. To avoid deformation on these films during the manufacturing process, the width of the structural layers that are placed beneath should likewise be the same. Figure 3 presents a manufactured stacked laminate prior to the addition of the sensing system. As ILSS testing is only conducted to verify the adhesion properties of the laminates, even if these contain embedded sensing films, the data will not be recorded, and all layers, both structural and sensitive, will have the same dimensions. Overall, 60 test specimens were manufactured, belonging 10 to each of the six groups. The dimensions of all manufactured samples are presented in Table 1.

Figure 3 - Stacking sequence used for manufacture of CFRP tensile test specimens with EML

Table 1 - Dimensions for ILSS and tensile test subjects

Sample group	Length (mm)	Width (mm)	Thickness (mm)
G1-T	250	25	2.44 ± 0.0583
G2-T			2.49 ± 0.0772
G3-T			2.46 ± 0.0756
G1-ILSS	27.5 ± 0.5	13.75 ± 0.25	2.75 ± 0.05
G2-ILSS	30.5 ± 0.5	15.25 ± 0.25	3.05 ± 0.05
G3-ILSS	28.2 ± 0.4	14.4 ± 0.2	2.82 ± 0.04

All the samples submitted to tensile tests will contain a single conventional SG (equal to the ones present in EML and PI sensing films) mounted on their surfaces. By comparing the obtained strain data between G1-T, G2-T and G3-T it is possible to assess the effect of the embedded resin layers and PI layers,

present in G2-T and G3-T respectively, on the tensile properties of the CFRP samples. On the other hand, the comparison between internal strains and external strains can be used to validate the sensing performance of EML. Representative ILSS and tensile test specimens are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 – Examples of final test samples: a) CFRP specimen with EML for tensile test; b) CFRP specimen with embedded PI film for tensile test; c) Bulk CFRP samples for ILSS tests; d) CFRP samples with EML for ILSS testing

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Results and discussion

Composite specimens belonging to groups G1-T, G2-T and G3-T, each representative of a specific condition, were submitted to tensile testing in a MTS Criterion model 45 universal testing machine at a crosshead velocity of 2 mm/min, using a load cell of 250 kN, and 180 mm as initial distance between grips. The SGs used in this work contain two grids, allowing the simultaneous measurement of both longitudinal and transversal displacements and the determination of the Poisson's ratio (ν_{12}), alongside the Young's modulus of the composite in the longitudinal (E_1) and transverse directions of the fibers, depending on the orientation of the fabric layers of the samples used in the tensile tests.

3.1.1 EML internal circuit validation

To validate the EML strain monitoring mechanism, the respective internal data was compared with the corresponding one obtained from surface SG. Figure 5, for sample reference G2-T3, shows the stress/strain curves (Figure 5 a)), derived from longitudinal strain data, and transversal strains (Figure 5 b)), respectively.

Figure 5 - Comparison between EML mechanism and conventional surface SG during tensile test on sample referenced G2-T3: a) Stress/Strain curve; b) Transversal strain

As can be observed in Figure 5 a), the evolution of stress during the tensile tests is extremely alike considering strain data of both EL and conventional SG sensing methods. The slight differences that are observed starting from 4000 µε can be attributed to the fact that both SGs are measuring strains in different surfaces, with the internal SG from the EML measuring the deformation of the embedded epoxy substrate, while the external one is monitoring directly on the carbon surface. Other factors, such as the different location of the sensors in the laminate, potential contamination of the internal tracks with the impregnated epoxy, eventual deformations imposed on the printed ink during the tensile test and the different conductors that are used (metal cables for the conventional surface SG and conductive silver ink for the embedded SG), which may have different associated electrical resistivity, can potentially contribute to the small observed deviations between both sensors. When comparing the linearity of both data sets with the Pearson correlation coefficient, a matching of $\approx 99.83\%$ is obtained indicating very good match. E_1 was calculated in accordance with ASTM D3039/D3039M in which its value corresponds to the slope of the stress/strain curve between strains of 1000 µε and 3000 µε. For the G2-T3, the measured E_1 from the surface was 96.72 GPa, while the one calculated with data from EML was 95.43, amounting to a final error of 1.3% between the two sensing mechanisms. Overall, considering all the CFRP samples, the average longitudinal moduli measured with EML was $97.6 \text{ GPa} \pm 4,74$, while in the surface a mean value of $100 \text{ GPa} \pm 0.105$ was determined, with a very small corresponding error of 4.21 ± 2.66 , attesting for rather satisfactory performance of the internal strain monitoring mechanism. Likewise, transverse strains could also be measured with a certain degree of precision with EML, as can be observed in Figure 5 b). These values are negative, since the samples under tensile test tend to shrink, alongside the respective internal and external mounted SGs. Using transverse strains between 1000 µε and 3000 µε it is possible to calculate ν_{12} with the data from the EML and the surface mounted SG, obtaining, respectively, 0.34 ± 0.0396 and 0.29 ± 0.0425 , which translates to an error of approximately 14.7%. This larger error is expected since strain in the transverse direction is more dependent on the behavior of the matrix, which is more susceptible to variability due to matrix cracking or fiber-matrix. Furthermore, considering that the SGs are placed in different locations and measuring strains in different surfaces, with the one from EML being mounted on a flexible epoxy layer, a higher deviation between the external and internal transverse strain may not be fully unexpected and could explain the slight higher deviation of ν_{12} in relation with E_1 .

3.1.2 Tensile properties of CFRP laminates with EML

Upon verifying the performance of embedded SG sensing circuits in CFRP composites laminates, it was necessary to verify just how does EML affects the mechanical behavior of the host structural composite. This comparison was made by studying thirty CFRP laminated samples, distributed equally across three different conditions (G1-T, G2-T and G3-T), with all of them containing a surface mounted bi-axial SG for the determination of E_1 and ν_{12} . The results from the tensile tests are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 - Final values of E_1 , ν_{12} and ultimate tensile strength for different CFRP tensile test sampling groups.

CFRP sample group	E_1 (GPa)	ν_{12}	Ultimate tensile strength (MPa)
G1-T	105 ± 3.98	0.301 ± 0.0398	925 ± 60.4
G2-T	99.1 ± 4.83	0.311 ± 0.0525	875 ± 8.85
G3-T	96.8 ± 3.08	0.312 ± 0.0650	808 ± 54.5

The insertion of both EML and monitoring PI films has seemingly minimal effect on E_1 and ν_{12} values. When comparing the average E_1 obtained from samples belonging to G2-T and G3-T groups with the control group G1-T, the modulus decreases, respectively, 5.62% and 7.81%. Comparing G1-T with G2-T and G3-T regarding the obtained average values for ν_{12} , it can be attested that the latter increases 3.32% and 3.65%, respectively. The differences between the analyzed groups of CFRP laminates seem to be more noticeable when analyzing the ultimate tensile strength, where, in comparison with the control group G1-T, samples from G2-T showed a reduction in this parameter of approximately 5.41%, whereas the ones belonging to G3-T exhibited a decrease around 12.65%. Since the substrate of the monitoring technique is the only testing parameter that is different across the three types of samples, it can seemingly be attested that while the monitoring technique itself may exert reduction of the mechanical properties of CFRP composites, these effects may be dampened with the application of the epoxy layer substrate corresponding to the material used as the matrix.

The results demonstrated in Table 2 can be better understood through the visualization of representative stress/strain curves in Figure 6, where, once again, it seems that the introduction of the embedded monitoring layer in CFRP laminates does not significantly affect E_1 and ν_{12} , as the slopes for all three curves, calculated for strains between 1000 $\mu\epsilon$ and 3000 $\mu\epsilon$, is nearly coincident.

Figure 6 - Comparison of Stress/Strain curves obtained for the different CFRP sampling groups

Slightly higher differences are observed as the tensile samples approach their respective ultimate tensile strength, where it is possible that the inclusion of the SG monitoring circuits could be the main factor in the reduction of this parameter in CFRP laminates belonging to both groups G2-T and G3-T. The advantage in using the proposed epoxy substrate for the EML, regarding the mechanical properties, could be the usage of the thin epoxy film itself, where the latter can sustain slightly higher tensile stress, with the average maximum stress obtained for G2-T being approximately 7.65% higher than the one observed in G3-T CFRP samples.

3.2 Interlaminar shear strength test

One important aspect that must be assessed when inserting the EML inside CFRP laminates, is the effect it may have on the adhesion with the remaining structural plies of the host composite. To that end, ILSS tests were also conducted on CFRP laminated specimens, split between G1-ILSS, G2-ILSS and G3-ILSS, in agreement with ISO 14130:1997 standard. Adhesion can be evaluated with this test, as specimens with small support span lengths are submitted to three-point bending. The apparent interlaminar shear strength (τ) is calculated using (1), where F is the failure load in N, b the width of the composite in mm and h is the thickness of the composite in mm.

$$\tau = \frac{3}{4} \times \frac{F}{bh} \quad (1)$$

The samples are submitted to three point bending at a testing velocity of 1 mm/min, with pre-load of 10 kN, in the universal testing machine Shimadzu Autograph AGX.

Before calculating τ , it is necessary to evaluate the failure mode of the samples. To properly assess the adhesion, the samples have to fail either from single shear or multiple shear, which represent the occurrence of delamination (Figure 7). Four samples of the G1-ILSS group, however, exhibited compression failure, thus rendering their respective results unusable, according to ISO 14130:1997 standard. As all specimens from G2-ILSS and G3-ILSS, which contain respectively the EML and the PI sensing film, presented either single shear or multiple instances of shear, a potential indicator that the embedded monitoring devices could affect adhesion. The calculated results for τ are shown, for each of the tested conditions, in Table 3.

Figure 7 - Single shear and multiple shear failure observed in CFRP samples after ILSS test

Table 3 – Calculated values for τ

CFRP sample group	T (MPa)
G1-ILSS	38.2 ± 2.64
G2-ILSS	37.9 ± 1.12
G3-ILSS	19.5 ± 1.75

From the values obtained for τ , it can be attested that the adhesion properties of composites with embedded monitoring mechanisms are heavily reliant on the substrate of the embedded film. This is due to the fact that the G1-ILSS and G2-ILSS have extremely similar values for τ , with the insertion of EML reducing this value, in average, by approximately 0.785%, whereas the embedment of PI sensing films decreased τ nearly in half by 48.9%. The near coincidence in the results observed for G1-ILSS and G2-ILSS in addition to the extremely large reduction of τ calculated for G3-ILSS seem to indicate that the circuit itself might not affect the adhesion of the overall adhesion of the composite, since it is presented only in G2-ILSS. As such, the main factor that can alter τ could most likely be the substrate used for the

embedded sensing devices, where the PI is vastly outperformed by the thin epoxy film. This is explained by the high mechanical and chemical compatibility of the epoxy that was utilized in the production of EML, which is equal to the resin used for the matrix of the composite.

For a better evaluation of the results shown in Table 3, τ was plotted in relation to the displacement as shown in Figure 8, considering representative ILSS samples from each of the conditions that were studied. There seems to be a good agreement with the values calculated for τ , as the curve for the G3-ILSS is well below the ones from G1-ILSS and G2-ILSS, once more alluding that the PI film could severely affect the interlaminar adhesion of the composite. While this issue with PI can be potentially solved or mitigated with surface treatments, in accordance with the results obtained from the ILSS tests, the epoxy substrate of the EML has seemingly residual effect on the adhesion properties of the host composite, without needing surface treatment.

Figure 8 - Plot of τ in relation to the displacement for representative samples.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the design, validation and effects of a new proposed EML for real-time monitoring of composite laminated structures was presented. The sensing mechanism was obtained by developing a reliable and repeatable variant of the typical VBI technique that is commonly applied for the production of high-end composite materials. Using that same process, it is possible to create multifunctional composites with EML. Regarding the performance of the internal sensors in measuring strains, it could be observed, from the conduction of tensile tests, that the EML sensing approach was able to precisely measure both transversal and longitudinal strains. Moreover, from the same tests, it was possible to determine that EML and the more common PI sensing films have low effect on the mechanical properties of the CFPR composites, with E_1 decreasing 5.62% in G2-T specimens and 7.81% in G3-T specimens. The main differences were observed when assessing the influence of the embedded mechanisms in the adhesion of the composite, where it was possible to observe, even before analyzing the data from the tests, that the insertion of the layers could prompt the occurrence of delamination. However, from the analysis of τ , it was possible to verify that the EML outperformed the PI sensing film in preservation of the adhesion properties, where samples from G2-ILSS presented reduction in τ inferior to 1%, whereas in samples from G3-ILSS, this increase was almost 50%.

More studies are still needed to evaluate the effect that the developed EMLs can have on composite materials under bending and impact testing. Additionally, the EML concept needs to be studied with other sensors, such as piezoelectric ones for real-time monitoring of vibrations or impact events, to ensure it can be applied in a wide range of scenarios.

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